

Performance and Structure of Microstrip Patch Antenna for Wireless Communication

Sadbhawana Jain

Assistant Professor

Electronics & Communication Engineering
Madhyanchal Professional University, Bhopal

sadbhawanajain@gmail.com

Abstract: *Wideband communication requires a microstrip antenna that is lightweight, simple to manufacture, and tiny in size. The current concept is for developing a microstrip antenna with a basic geometrical design that would provide respectable broadband. The design study of a microstrip antenna with a rectangular or square shape is presented in the paper. For feeding, both antennas made use of microstrip line. In comparison to rectangular microstrip, the square microstrip antenna provides a broader bandwidth and adequate return loss. The small antenna is designed to work in the X band of frequencies. The suggested microstrip antenna has a large 500 MHz bandwidth and a significant -24 dB return loss. Numerous X-band wideband utilities make use of this large bandwidth.*

Keywords: *Broadband, Microstrip Antenna, Reflection coefficient, Stub Matching.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of a Microstrip antenna in wireless communication systems is a success and meets the demand of the most recent generation of wireless communication technology in line with new innovation. Each of these devices uses microstrip antennas due of their various benefits, including their extremely low cost, simple construction, and high efficiency [1]. Its disadvantage, meanwhile, is a small operational bandwidth, which places limitations on how it can be used in wireless systems [2]. Wireless devices and broadband applications that perform a variety of jobs have emerged as essential components of our daily correspondence lives. As a result, the need for low profile wideband has been reduced [3]. The use of a microstrip antenna satisfies the majority of criteria for mobile and satellite equipment as well as several corporate requirements. The amount of electronic circuits needed for wireless applications is clearly decreasing, and the microstrip is a very good fit for this. The size of the antennas utilised in the majority of applications is also substantially decreasing. Microstrip antenna fix design satisfies these requirements. It was discovered that suitable impedance bandwidth of the microstrip

antenna can be one factor for improvement after considering various strategies [4-6]. Notches' carving effect [7,8]

and numerous investigations have shown that slots [9-11] are present in its broadening. Using a dielectric substrate as the foundation and a radiating conducting material itched on the substrate's upper side, a very simple form of the microstrip antenna can be built. For the sake of streamlining the study and making performance predictions, the radiating conducting material can take on any basic geometrical shape.

II. ANTENNA DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

The proper substrate identification and selection of the working frequency are the first steps in planning the microstrip antenna. The antenna's operating frequency must be wisely selected. The intended antenna must operate inside the desired frequency band. 11GHz, which is in the X-band region, is chosen as the operating frequency in our design. The selection of an acceptable substrate is the next step in the antenna shaping process. The antenna's electromagnetic characteristics have a stable impact on the substrate's height and dielectric [12]. Duroid was chosen as the dielectric material for the design. The antenna's dimensions are inversely proportional to the dielectric constant, hence a high dielectric substrate causes a reduction in those dimensions [13]. Microstrip feedline is the current feeding technique.

The length, L, and width, W, of the antenna are found out by using the following equations.

$$W = \frac{c}{2f} \times \sqrt{\frac{2}{(\epsilon_r + 1)}}$$
$$L = \frac{c}{2f} \left(\frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \sqrt{\left[1 + 12 \frac{h}{W} \right]} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} - 2\Delta L$$

Here, ϵ_r is the dielectric constant of the substrate.

The chosen substrate, wideband, is Duroid with ϵ_r of 3, and the working frequency, f , is taken to be 11 GHz. The effective length is subjected to the correction factor, ΔL , and this correction factor is found to be nearly 0.07.

The corresponding length, L_G , and the width W_G , of the substrate is in correspondence with its height, h ,

$$W_G = W + 6h$$

$$L_G = L + 6h$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The design of two sets of antenna structures are shown here, along with simulations of the proposed antenna performed using the HFSS software. One has a rectangular shape, while the other has a square antenna.

The width and length of the patch of the microstrip antenna have been calculated as 11 mm and 9 mm, respectively, in light of the aforementioned formulae. The substrate is 1.57 mm in height. The length (L_s) and breadth (W_s) of the substrate plane are assumed to be 48 mm and 48 mm, respectively. The HFSS tool has been used for simulation.

The height of the substrate in the first set of observations ranges from 1.17 mm to 2.47 mm. The corresponding reflection coefficient and bandwidth is tabulated in table 1.

Height (h) (mm)	Bandwidth (MHz)	Reflection coefficient (-db)
1.17	350	18.5
1.37	360	22.5
1.57	460	25
1.77	430	38
2.47	510	15.5

Table 1: Bandwidth and reflection coefficients at different height

At a height of 1.17 mm, 350 MHz of bandwidth and -18.5 dB of reflection coefficient had been measured. The simulation reveals that when the height of the substrate rises from 1.17 mm to 1.57 mm, the antenna resonates at a frequency of 10.8 GHz and exhibits a

max
refl
ante
increased from 1.57 mm to 1.77 mm. The highest reflection coefficient of -38 dB is achieved with a substrate height of 1.77 mm, however the bandwidth is slightly decreased. Figure 1 depicts a plot of the bandwidth and reflection coefficient for an antenna with various substrate heights.

Fig 1: Bandwidth and Reflection coefficient with different height

In all further design, the height of the substrate is kept at 1.57 mm.

A. Rectangular Antenna Design

Figure 2 depicts the fundamental design of the first set of rectangular-shaped microstrip antennas intended for 11 GHz. The resonating patch has dimensions of 11 mm in width and 9 mm in length. The feeding element's width is 0.8 mm. The ground plane's dimensions for the substrate plane are 18 mm and 20 mm, respectively. As illustrated in Figure 2, this structure has a 340 MHz bandwidth and a -17 dB reflection coefficient.

Fig 2: Rectangular type-1 Antenna

Fig 3: Bandwidth and Reflection coefficient of Rectangular type-1 Antenna

Fig 4: Rectangular type-2 Antenna

Figure 4 depicts the type-2 rectangular microstrip antenna structure. The feedline in this antenna has been altered by the inclusion of a stub on the source side. The bandwidth is raised to 400 MHz with a reflection coefficient of -18 dB, as illustrated in figure 4, and this result is well-matched.

Fig 5: Bandwidth and Reflection coefficient of Rectangular type-2 antenna with stub feedline.

B. Square Antenna Design

We used the same geometry while designing a square antenna as we did for a rectangle antenna. The side (length and width) of this design structure is 9 mm, while the side of the substrate plane is 28 mm. In figures 6 and 8, the ground plane is depicted as having a square shape. Simple feedline is depicted in the first illustration, whereas stub feedline is shown in the second.

Fig 6: Square type-1 Antenna

The square type 1 antenna exhibits a strong -29 dB reflection coefficient and a 430 GHz bandwidth. The outcome is displayed in figure 8. The bandwidth is increased to 500 MHz in a square type-2 antenna with a stub feedline, and the resulting reflection coefficient is -24 dB. Therefore, a 70 MHz improved bandwidth is gained by adding stub at the source side. In figure 9, this outcome is displayed.

Fig 7: Bandwidth and Reflection coefficient of Squaretype-1 Antenna

Fig 8: Square type-2 Antenna with stub feedline

Fig 9: Bandwidth and Reflection coefficient of Square type-2 Antenna with stub feedline

The table 2, summarized the design results.

Type of antenna	Height (h)(mm)	Bandwidth (MHz)	Reflection coefficient (-dB)
Rectangular	1.17	340	17
Rectangular	1.37	400	18
Square	1.57	430	29
Square	1.77	500	24

Table 2: Summary of the results for various antenna structures.

IV. CONCLUSION

The suggested microstrip square antenna has a nice broader bandwidth of 500 MHz and a stub feedline. Additionally, with a substrate height of 1.57 mm, it displays a high reflection coefficient of -24 dB. This supports every element of how the various antenna structures were designed. By properly impedance matching a stub feedline at the antenna's source point, the antenna can be made wider. There are several wireless applications that could benefit from this good bandwidth and high return loss. A straightforward antenna would be useful for wide-band wireless applications.

REFERENCES

1. John Colaco, Rajesh B. Lohani, "Performance analysis of microstrip patch antenna using a four-layered substrate of different materials", <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.11.522>, Volume 52, Part 3, Pages 1891-1900, 2022.
2. Nada N. Tawfeeq, Sawsan D. Mahmood, "Simulation study of microstrip antenna for 2.45 GHz applications based on octagon shaped", <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.12.560>, Volume 42, Part 5, Pages 2448-2456, 2021.
3. S. Mohideen Abdul Kadhar, A. Yasodai, "Microstrip patch antenna design for wireless network applications", <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.11.125>, Volume 45, Part 2, Pages 2518-2523, 2021.
4. R. Mishra, R. G. Mishra, A. K. Shrivastav, "Design and Analysis of Microstrip Patch Antenna for Wireless Communication", International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE) ISSN: 2278-3075, Volume-8 Issue-7 May, 2019.

5. H. Kaschel and C Ahumada, "Design of a triband antenna microstrip for 2.4 GHz 3.5 GHz and 5.7 GHz applied a WBAN", IEEE Conference on CHILECON, pp. 1-7, Oct. 2017.
6. Rizwan Masood, Christian Person and Ronan Sauleau, "A

Dual-Mode DualPort Pattern Diversity Antenna for 2.45-GHz WBAN", IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagations Letters, vol. 16, pp. 1064-1067, 2017.

7. David Ferreira, Pedro Pires, Ruben Rodrigues and Rafael F. S. Caldeirinha, "Wearable Textile Antennas: Examining the effect of bending on their performance", IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine, vol. 59, pp. 5459, 2017.
8. Jinpil Tak, Seungmin Woo, Jaekwang Kwon and Jaehoon Choi, "Dual-Band Dual-Mode Patch Antenna for On-/Off-Body WBAN Communications", IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters, vol. 15, pp. 348-351, 2016.
9. S. Yan and G. A. E. Vandenbosch, "Wearable antenna with tripolarisation diversity for WBAN communications", IET Electronics Letters, vol. 52, pp. 500-502, 2016.
10. Andrea Ruaro, Jesper Thaysen and Kaj B. Jakobsen, "Wearable Shell Antenna for 2.4 GHz Hearing Instruments", IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 64, pp. 2127-2135, 2016.
11. X. Zhu, Y. Guo and W. Wu, "A Compact Dual-Band Antenna for Wireless Body-Area Network Applications", IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagations Letters, vol. 15, pp. 98-101, 2016.
12. R. B. V. B. Simorangkir, S. M. Muzahir and K. P. Esselle, "A Printed UWB Antenna with Full Ground Plane for WBAN Applications", IEEE International Antenna Technology (iWAT), March. 2016.
13. Y. Jin and J. Choi, "Compact dual-band antenna for smart wristband application", IEEE on RF and Wireless Technologies for Biomedical and Healthcare Applications, pp. 186187, Sep. 2015.